

TECHNOLOGY OF OBTAINING DRY LYOPHILIC EXTRACT OF DESERT SAGE (*SALVIA DESERTA SHANGIN.*)

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Relevance: Medicinal plant raw materials are an important source of biologically active substances, which is why dry forms are preferred for the creation of phytopharmaceuticals due to their stability, ease of dosing, and storage. The most promising method for obtaining such forms is lyophilization, as lyophilized extracts are superior to conventional dry extracts due to their preservation of thermolabile biologically active substances, better solubility, stability during storage, lightweight structure, precise dosing, and longer shelf life. Among the promising plants, the little-studied desert sage (*Salvia deserta* Schangin.), which grows in Southern Kazakhstan, is of particular interest. Only medicinal sage is officially registered in Kazakhstan and included in the State Pharmacopoeia, other types of sage are poorly studied and are not used in medicine. Extracts of the desert sage root have antiplatelet, antimicrobial, and immunomodulatory effects. In this regard, the study of new poorly studied species of sage is an urgent problem. The development of technology for obtaining lyophilic extracts of desert sage is an urgent task.

The purpose of the study is to develop a technology for obtaining lyophilic extract of desert sage.

Materials and methods. To obtain the extract, dried and crushed aboveground parts of desert sage collected in the foothills of Southern Kazakhstan were used. To isolate biologically active substances, the method of ultrasonic extraction with 40% alcohol was used, followed by the removal of the extractant on a rotary evaporator. Next, the resulting thick extract was lyophilized in a Harvest Right apparatus, USA. The quality of the extract was determined by physico-chemical, technological and microbiological methods.

Results. Biologically active substances were isolated by ultrasonic extraction, and a thick extract was obtained by distilling the extractant on a vacuum rotary evaporator, which was freeze-dried to obtain a dry extract.

Extracts obtained with a 40% aqueous alcohol solution have a higher yield of extractive substances (3.7% more) compared to extracts obtained with 70% ethyl alcohol. Freeze drying provides a higher yield of dry lyophilic extract (15.7%) and better solubility compared to drying in a drying cabinet (14.1%). All samples were characterized by hygroscopicity and absence of excess heavy metal content and microbiological purity.

Conclusions. As a result of the use of innovative technology, a lyophilic extract of desert sage was obtained and the main pharmacological and technological characteristics of the dry extract were established.